

AGRICULTURAL SCIENCES

ISSUES OF ENSURING WORLD FOOD SECURITY

Hajiyeva A.,
Saliyeva V.,
Huseynova S.,
Abbaszade N.
head teacher

Azerbaijan State Agrarian University

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Abstract

The intensive growth of the population in the world requires increasing the stock of food products. In modern times, food security is the basis of the economic and political position of every country. It is one of the most important problems of the day that people in the world suffer from food shortages and taking preventive measures for this. The solution to this problem can be overcome by increasing the productivity of agricultural plants.

In the article, the main factors of ensuring food safety are analyzed as an important aspect of national and economic security. Information on food balances of crop and animal husbandry products and directions for solving the main problems of food production are indicated in the field of provision for the main types of products.

Keywords: national security, food security, agricultural products, food products, grain.

Introduction

One of the main tasks facing every country is ensuring food security, which is an important area of national security. Ensuring food and food safety covers quite wide and multifaceted problems. The history of various countries shows that a negative attitude to the problem can lead to social unrest that undermines the foundations of the state. Since ensuring food security is directly related to the agricultural sector, improving the work of the agricultural sector is one of the priority issues in solving this problem.

As we know, food products demanded by the country's population are mainly produced and processed in agricultural production areas. Improving the quality of strategically important products - cereals and technical plants, as well as fruits and vegetables, meat and dairy products, expanding their production, packing and storing them in clean and hygienic conditions is one of the most important things that can be done in the direction of ensuring food safety. Food and food safety includes complex measures that ensure continuous, long-term and sustainable satisfaction of the population's demand for basic food products according to established quality standards.

Food security, being a global problem, is economic, social, technological, geographical, historical, political, etc. formed by the influence of factors, and the solution to this problem was related to the implementation of socio-economic, political, technical-technological, ecological policy. It is natural that in the approach to food security, the presence of natural resources and their effective use, as well as the role of the state in the economy and the correct formation of the policy, play a decisive role has[2].

The complexity of the food and food supply situation in the country and the dependence on foreign markets require the implementation of a number of urgent measures aimed at ensuring the safety of individual types of food products. It is known that in accordance

with the requirements of the market economy, a large number of private economic entities have been formed in the agricultural sector. Family-peasant farms, which are the leading force in the field of agriculture, play an important role in the formation of the country's food and nutrition resources, and in the production of a wide variety of products in different regions. At the same time, there is a need for financial support in accordance with the concept of Sustainable Development in the activities of rural farms [1].

The availability of food and food products from an economic and physical point of view, the ability of the population to buy these products in all residential areas of the country, or the provision of the organization of nutrition in a volume and variety that is not less than the rational norms for the consumption of food products is related to the level of infrastructure development [5].

The main factors of world food security.

The main factors of ensuring the country's food security include the following:

- the level of production of food and food products in the country;
- economic feasibility of food and food products production;
- the level of prices of food and food products;
- purchasing power of the country's population;
- average monthly income and salary of the population;
- concessions and allowances.

The safety of food and food products is always very important for people's economic-social, healthy and active life. Food security is ensured when people always have access to enough quality food and nutrition products to lead an active and healthy lifestyle. The solution to the problem of food and food safety in each country is related to the reduction of poverty in the country, the safety of food products and the efficiency of the use of food products [3].

Research shows that an important aspect of the formation of the food market and the improvement of product quality in market conditions is the improvement of the quality management system. Because quality management, which is an important element of production management, reflects the increase of economic indicators of production. At the same time, effective quality management is of great economic importance [4].

In terms of meeting the demand for food products, the main indicators in assessing the potential capabilities of the country are the volume of production, the volume of consumption per capita, the self-sufficiency of the country with its main products, the level of import and export. The country's self-sufficiency level with food products is determined by the ratio of total production to consumption, the percentage indicator compared to the physiological food norm.

The results of studies conducted by the "Economist Intelligence Unit" (EIU) are widely used in global food security assessments. The Global Food Security Index (GFSI) is calculated by this institution.

The Global Food Security Index examines food availability, availability, quality and safety, natural resources and sustainability in 113 countries. The index is a dynamic quantitative and qualitative benchmarking model built from 58 unique indicators that measure key drivers of food security in both developing and developed countries.

The GFSI concept understands food security as a three-dimensional entity. The three dimensions here are affordability, accessibility, and quality/safety. Affordability is described as the ability of a country's population to pay for food and the costs they may face both when food supplies are stable and during food shocks. Availability is a country's ability to produce and distribute food, including risks of food shortages. Quality and safety refer to average food quality and the food safety environment of each country.

The latest edition of the GFSI includes a natural resources and sustainability component in the main index. This category assesses a country's exposure to the effects of a changing climate, characterizes its vulnerability to natural resource risks and how the country is adapting to these risks. A sustainability component was first introduced as an adjustment factor to the GFSI in 2017, and has been generalized for the first time given its growing importance. The food and food security indicators in the mentioned study differ from the indicators adopted by the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO) for the assessment of food security. These indicators include physical availability of food, economic access to food, food insecurity, food quality and safety. This approach shows that food and food safety indicators are really related to different areas, and only a system based on solid foundations in each of these areas will ensure the safety of food and food products.

Table 1.

Indicators used in the calculation of the Global Food Security Index

Affordability	Measures consumers' ability to buy food, their vulnerability to price shocks, and the existence of programs and policies to support consumers when shocks occur
Availability	Measures national food security adequacy, risk of supply disruptions, national capacity for food distribution, and research efforts to expand agricultural production
Quality and safety	It measures average nutrient diversity and food quality, as well as food safety
Natural resources and sustainability	It assesses the country's exposure to the effects of climate change, determines its vulnerability to natural resource risks and how the country is adapting to these risks.

Data source: [6]

In the world, Ireland, Austria, Great Britain, Finland, Switzerland, Netherlands, Canada, Japan, France and the USA share the top 10 with a total GFS-2021 score in the range of 77.8 and 80 points on the index.

According to GFS-2021, Azerbaijan's ranking was 56th among 113 countries. The ranking indicators of the Global Food Security Index in Azerbaijan for 2021 are given in Table 2:

Table 2. Global Food Security Index ranking for Azerbaijan, 2021

Global ranking	Country	General assessment	Affordability	Availability	Quality and safety	Natural resources and sustainability
56	Azerbaijan	62,6	82,3	58,0	59,1	38,2

Data source : [6]

Agricultural products worth 9 billion 163.4 million manats were produced in Azerbaijan in 2021, which is 3.4% more than the indicator of 2020. Of this, animal husbandry amounted to 4 billion 652.4 million manats, 4 billion 511 million manats agricultural products were produced. The production volume of livestock products increased by 2.8%, and the production volume of vegetable products increased by 4%.

According to the State Statistics Committee, 1 million 815.5 thousand tons of vegetables (increase of 4.4%) were collected. 1.062 million tons of potatoes (increase of 2.3%), 3 million 363 thousand tons of cereals and legumes, including corn, were harvested from the fields. products (increase of 3.3%), 1 million 885.4

thousand tons of wheat (productivity 32.9 centners), 459.9 thousand tons of melon products (increase of 2.6%), 1 million 204.9 thousand tons of fruits and berries (increase of 6.3%), 209.8 thousand tons of grapes (increase of 0.9%), 1 thousand 177.7 tons of green tea leaves (increase of 26.4%), 193.2 thousand tons of sugar beet (decrease of 23, 7%), 286.7 thousand tons of cotton (14.9% decrease), 25.8 thousand tons of sunflower (4.2% increase) and 6.4 thousand tons of tobacco (7.7% decrease) were harvested.[12]

Considering the provision of food security of our republic as one of the main goals of the economic strategy, the government of Azerbaijan takes continuous

steps to further improve production opportunities in the agricultural sector.

Information on food balances of crop and live-stock products in the supply area for the main types of crops in the world.

In order to evaluate the situation related to food and food security in the world, the information of food balances of agricultural and livestock products is of great importance. Among the strategic products for ensuring food security, grain occupies the main place. Cereals are the main source of food and fodder for both humans and animals. Major grains include wheat, rice, and corn, which form the basis of staple diets around the world. One of the most cultivated and consumed cereals, wheat is the main ingredient in various products such as bread, pasta and bakery products.

Maize, rice, wheat, barley and sorghum are the five most widely produced cereal crops. Maize showed a peak production of 1.2 billion tons in 2021 and the fastest growth since 2000, 104% more than other major grains, as it is used more widely in the biofuel and animal feed sectors. Rice and wheat had very similar production levels and growth rates: 787 million tons in 2021 and 32% more since 2000 for rice and 771 million tons and 31% more for wheat. Barley and sorghum had fairly stable production over time, with an 8% decline for barley between 2020 and 2021.[8]

Currently, the main wheat producers in the world are China, India, Russia, USA and France. About 52 % of the global wheat production is accounted for by these countries.

In 2021, the Americas were the top producing region for maize, with the United States of America and Brazil accounting together for 39% of the world production. China was the second largest producer, with a share of almost 23%. Asia was the leader for rice production, with the top three producers in the region: China 27 % of the global total, India 25% and Bangladesh 7%. Asia also accounted for a large share of the global wheat volumes with China 18% of the world total and India 14%. The Russian Federation was the third largest wheat producer in 2021, with 10% of the global production.[8]

Potatoes were the most produced commodity in the group, with 376 million tonnes in 2021, (up 17 percent compared with 2000), followed by cassava with 315 million tonnes (up 79 percent compared with 2000). The production of each of the other three highest ranked tubers was below 100 million tonnes in 2021, with different trends: the production of sweet potatoes declined by 36 percent between 2000 and 2021, while that of yams and taro grew by 90 percent and 17 percent, respectively. Roots and tubers were mainly produced in Africa and Asia, at around 340 million tonnes in both regions that account for around 80 percent of the global production.[8]

China is currently the world's largest fruit and vegetable producer and among the top four developing country exporters of fresh vegetables.

If we look at the total volume of world fruit production, we will see that it has increased by 59% from

2000 to 2021. The aggregate world fruit production recorded a growth of 59 % from 2000 to 2021 with a total production volume in 2021 of 910 million tonnes. Bananas were the most produced fruit with 125 million tonnes in 2021, followed by watermelons 102 million tonnes, apples 93 million tonnes, oranges 76 million tonnes, and grapes 74 million tonnes. The global production of vegetables went up 68% during the same period, reaching 1.15 billion tonnes in 2021. Tomatoes ranked as the most produced vegetable with 189 million tonnes in 2021, followed by onions 107 million tonnes, including shallots, cucumbers 93 million tonnes, including gherkins, cabbages 71 million tonnes and eggplants 59 million tonnes.[8]

Chicken, pork and cattle were the main meats produced in the world, accounting for 316 million tons in 2021.

Chicken, pig, cattle, sheep and goat were the main type of meat produced between 2000 and 2021 , accounting in 2021 for 93 % (331 million tonnes) of the total meat production. The production of chicken meat grew the fastest over the period (+107 %, to 122 million tonnes in 2021) and overtook the production of pig meat in 2019 as the African swine fever affected Asian countries; after declines in 2019 and 2020, pig meat production recovered in 2021 to 120 million tonnes, the same production level of 2017–2018. Meat of cattle, sheep and goat showed regular and steady growth, reaching 73, 10 and 6 million tonnes in 2021, respectively. At the regional level, Asia is the main producer of meat (43 % of the global total), followed by the Americas 31%, Europe 18%, Africa % and Oceania 2%. [8]

The main problems of food production in the world and directions for solving them.

Although the spectrum of global problems is wide, here the more serious universal ones are separated. Food supply of the population in the modern era is one of the most global problems of mankind. This problem also comes to the fore in terms of physiological requirements and life requirements directly related to people.

By 2050, the world's population is expected to increase by 2.2 billion, which means that the world's farmers will need to consume about 70% more than what is produced now. Therefore, a sustainable food security policy should be implemented and food waste should be reduced. It is estimated that 33-50% of the food produced globally today is never eaten, and the value of this wasted food is over \$1 trillion. Thus, every year, an area larger than the territory of China is used for the cultivation of inedible (wasted) food products. If we were to describe food waste as a country, then this country would be the third largest emitter of greenhouse gases after the United States and China. In addition to all these mentioned, there is also a huge shortage of food in our world. [9]

The Food and Agriculture Organization of the UN (FAO), the International Fund for Agricultural Development (IFAD) and the International Food Program (WFP) have determined that the average number of people facing hunger in the world in 2022 is approximately 735 million. The number of people facing hunger has increased by around 122 million since 2019 due

to the impact of multiple crises such as the COVID-19 epidemic, the war in Ukraine and climate shocks. Although global hunger figures will remain stable between 2021 and 2022, there is a deep food crisis in different parts of the world. Asia and Latin America have seen progress in reducing hunger. But in 2022, hunger is still on the rise in most regions of West Asia, the Caribbean and Africa. Africa, in particular, remains the region with the deepest hunger.

Grain farming occupies one of the main places in the solution of the problem. The state of grain production and its position in the grain market are considered as the main indicator of food security of individual countries on an international scale in world practice. From the point of view of the socio-economic importance of grain production for the country, the reliable supply of bread and bakery products to the population, its importance as an irreplaceable product in the daily consumer product, grain, which is a food product, once again comes to the fore. Grain and its processed products are the basis of human activity by origin.

It should be noted that the world production of grain decreased by more than 21 million tons in 2020, and this gave impetus to the rise in prices. The rise in the price of food and food products is not only an economic problem, but also a serious social problem. All countries of the world pay special attention to this issue.

The fundamental causes of global food price hikes have not been addressed, suggesting that price increases will continue for some time to come. Thus, there are a number of reasons that will affect how the prices of wheat, corn, rice, soybeans and other agricultural products will increase in 2022. The first and least predictable of them is the weather. In recent years, the intensity and strength of extreme weather events due to climate change have increased significantly. Last year was no exception in this sense. In 2021, extreme weather conditions such as drought, frost, and rain were observed in many regions of the world. All this had a serious impact on productivity. Therefore, this factor will always bring volatility to the market. The prices in the grain market are primarily formed depending on the volume of harvest in the main exporting countries. The second important factor is inflation. Since the beginning of the pandemic, all countries are struggling with its consequences, including making additional investments in the economy. Fuel, electricity and fertilizers have risen sharply in recent months. This will further increase the price of agricultural products [10].

The International Grain Council operates to stabilize and regulate the grain market, and the main goal of the council is international cooperation to stabilize the world grain market. This Council includes 23 countries and is based in London.

The International Grains Council (IGC) decreases its world grain production forecast for the 2023-24 marketing year. The International Grains Council (IGC) decreased its world grain production forecast for the 2023-24 marketing year by 2 million tonnes to 2.29 billion tonnes, which it said reflected recent dry weather. [11]

The agricultural sector acts as the main object of food security of the population. Therefore, the state

care directed to the center of gravity of solving the problem is imperative. Developed countries are well aware from their experience that agriculture is not competitive compared to other sectors of the economy due to many specific conditions. On this basis, they are constantly increasing state support to the field. In Europe and America, large amounts of subsidies are given to agriculture, and this sector is already considered costly, but important for the security and existence of the state, as well as the maintenance of the army and the state apparatus. Countries with a strong export potential of food products use this opportunity as a means of influencing other countries for their own interests. For this reason, ensuring the food security of the state is very important. That is, during emergency situations, the state should not become dependent on foreign countries in order to provide the population with food and food-stuffs. According to economic laws, if more than 25% of food products consumed in the country are imported from foreign countries, the food supply of that country is considered dangerous. It should also be noted that the number of countries importing food products is increasing. This is already an alarm signal for humanity.

The result

In conclusion, it should be noted once again that food security is an integral element of the country's national security, which must fully ensure the availability of food products to the population, as well as eliminate threats that negatively affect both the health of residents and the level of well-being of the country.

In order to ensure and further improve the food security of the population of the countries of the world, as well as to strengthen the food security during emergencies and natural disasters, relevant state institutions regularly carry out monitoring and measures. There is a need to continue these measures consistently, as well as to cover more types of products with those measures. Taking into account the demand of a unified world economic system, the implementation of a planned organization and regulation mechanism of production relations on a global international scale and in individual regions and countries is considered one of the necessary means for the effective use of natural resources and solving the food security problem. We consider it appropriate to abandon the production method based on the principle of spontaneous competition, and the opinions and opinions of economists conducting research in this field, in a situation where 1/5 of the world's population lives in conditions of food shortage and hunger, the population is growing rapidly, and natural resources are depleted. Planned and regulated production relations can be considered the main condition for solving the global problem of food security.

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